

Subject-Integrated Instructional Material for the Enhancement of the Least Mastered Reading Comprehension Skills among Grade Five Pupils

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to enhance the least mastered reading comprehension skills of Grade Five pupils in terms of identifying the main idea, sequencing of events, answering direct recall questions, predicting outcomes, and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. The main concern of this study is to improve the pupil's reading comprehension skills through the use of subject-integrated instructional material.

Meanwhile, the study revealed the mean pretest scores before using the subject-integrated instructional material were both Average in terms of identifying the main idea and predicting outcomes; Fair level in terms of answering direct recall questions and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary; sequencing of events found in the Poor level while in the post-test scores of the respondents after using the subject-integrated instructional materials revealed both Average in terms of identifying the main idea and answering direct recall questions; Fair level in terms of predicting outcomes and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary; in terms of sequencing of events still in Poor level despite of increase in the mean scores. However, the study also revealed that there is no significant difference before and after using the subject-integrated instructional material.

KEYWORDS: instructional material, least mastered skills, reading comprehension

INTRODUCTION

Learning to read is a key educational goal that helps students succeed. Reading skills are highly valued and important for individual opportunities. It is a skill that will empower everyone because it allows us to acquire new knowledge, enjoy literature and do the day-to-day things that are part of our lives.

Reading, listening, speaking, and writing are the four macro skills. Of the four skills listed, reading is one of the most challenging because many students have not been able to improve it. With reading, we need to understand the significance of just one word to understand the text we are going to read.

Based on DO 14, S. 2018 or the Policy Guidelines on the Administration of the Revised Philippine Informal Reading Inventory, every Filipino student must become a reader/ writer at their grade level [1]. Thus, DepEd administers Phil-IRI which aims to measure the level of reading performance of the learners in both English and Filipino.

However, reading is still one of the problems that was encountered nowadays in our country. The Philippines is reported as one of the countries that have poor reading skills this year because of the effect of the Covid-19 pandemic. In fact, there are only three students in every twenty, who can read the simple text because of the longest school closure as reported in Inquirer.Net. Some of the students can read but they did not understand it because they have poor word comprehension. In most cases, students have been promoted to the next grade, although they are not competent enough in reading because of the DepEd mass promotion policy. Aside from that, teachers nowadays face a big challenge in enhancing the reading comprehension skills of the students especially those who are in the intermediate level. In order to deliver the knowledge to the students, teachers used supplementary material in delivering a lesson.

As a basic tool for learning, reading comprehension facilitates the ability to reason, think, discriminate, judge, evaluate and solve what has been read. Reading comprehension among higher elementary-grade students is very essential for them to be effective and efficient in the classroom. They cannot perform well in the classroom when they have difficulty understanding what they have read (De Roxas, 2018) [2].

Reading comprehension will be developed by the students by practicing reading daily independently using supplementary material as part of the new mode of learning. This tool will help the teachers to monitor the student's progress in guiding students' individual approaches to learning. Having a love for reading could help them to gather information as well as understand the text. Furthermore, it will benefit the students in enhancing the least mastered skills in reading comprehension.

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OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To improve the least mastered reading comprehension skills of the grade five pupils through the use of subject-integrated instructional material.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used both descriptive and one-group pretest-posttest experimental research designs. The researchers used these methods because it deals with the perception of grade five students in using subject-integrated instructional material in terms of need-based, content, standard alignment (DepEd MELCs), integration, and graphics. This study also intended to identify whether using subject-integrated instructional material has an effect on the reading comprehension skills of the respondents.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were one section of Grade Five consisting of thirty-five (35) pupils at Canda Elementary School located in Canda, Sariaya, Quezon.

Sampling Technique

The respondents were purposively selected by their expected manifestation of enhanced reading comprehension skills and they are capable enough in giving judgment in using the subject-integrated instructional material.

Research Procedure

Before a letter of request for approval to conduct the study was handed personally by the researcher to the school principal of Canda Elementary School in Canda Sariaya, Quezon, the researcher formulated the instruments and it was validated by three (3) master teachers.

The researcher by then was ready for the administration of the reading assessments for the target respondents, letters duly signed by the principal of the school to conduct the study and for the administration of reading assessments were secured.

Upon the approval of the principal, the researcher was taking charge of the administration and distribution of the reading assessments to the respondents. The researcher distributed the pre-reading assessment to one section of grade five students for assessing their initial reading comprehension skills performance.

After the retrieval of the answered reading assessments, the researcher then gave the subject-integrated instructional material. Each topic in the material was in line with the researcher prepared lesson exemplar. The lessons were taught by the teacher to make sure that the students fully understand it. Then, the grade five students were answered it independently after each lesson. After 5 weeks of teaching and answering, the researcher then distributed the post-reading assessment to assess the reading comprehension skills of the respondents after using subject-integrated instructional material.

The accomplished pre- and post-reading assessments were sealed to ensure the confidentiality of contents.

Research Instrument

The pre-reading assessment was used to determine the initial reading comprehension performance of the pupils before using the subject-integrated instructional material. The main instrument in the study was the Subject-Integrated Instructional Material which serve as the supplementary material. Post-test was used to determine the effect of the instructional material after giving them to the respondents.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In terms of statistical tool in interpreting the data that was gathered for the study, the researcher used frequency and percent distribution to assess the pre and post reading assessment of the respondents before and after using subject-integrated instructional material. The researcher also used T-test to determine if there is a significant difference between the subject-integrated instructional material and the pupils' reading performance in terms of identifying the main idea, sequencing of events, answering direct recall questions, predicting outcomes and identifying the unfamiliar vocabulary.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Mean pretest score of the respondents before using subject-integrated instructional material.

Least Mastered Reading Comprehension Skills	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Identifying Main Idea	4.43	1.44	Average
Sequencing of Events	0.94	1.28	Poor
Answering Direct Recall Questions	3.40	2.53	Fair
Predicting Outcomes	4.23	2.41	Average
Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary	3.20	1.94	Fair

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Legend: 8.00 – 10.00 Excellent; 6.00 – 7.99 Good; 4.00 – 5.99 Average; 2.00 – 3.99 Fair; 0 – 1.99 Poor

Table 1 presents the results of the pretest of the respondents before using the subject-integrated instructional material. The reading performance of the respondents before the use of subject-integrated instructional material got Average in terms of identifying the main idea and predicting outcomes having different Mean of 4.43 and 4.23. It means that the students have a little difficulty with the topics thus they have to be improved. Meanwhile, answering direct recall questions had a Mean of 3.40, and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary got 3.2 having the same Fair level. This result means that the students need to do more exercises or practice reading about the topics. However, the sequencing of events got the lowest Mean of 0.94 and was found in at poor level. It implies that the students have a difficulty in identifying the correct sequence of the events in the paragraph or passages given to them. The study revealed that identifying Main Idea got the highest Mean of 4.43 which means this have a big impact in the reading comprehension skills of the learners. It was supported by the results of the study of Hare and Milligan (1984), Stevens et al. (2019) and Boudah (2013) [3]-[5]. Moreover, Bailey (2015), Sumirat et al. (2019) and Abadi (2020) noted that when it comes to predicting outcomes, it will become hard to the students if this skill will be neglected into practice [6]-[8].

Table 2. Mean posttest score of the respondents after using subject-integrated instructional material.

Least Mastered Reading Comprehension Skills	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Identifying Main Idea	4.80	1.97	Average
Sequencing of Events	1.77	1.80	Poor
Answering Direct Recall Questions	4.49	2.33	Average
Predicting Outcomes	3.74	2.31	Fair
Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary	2.31	1.62	Fair

Legend: 8.00 – 10.00 Excellent; 6.00 – 7.99 Good; 4.00 – 5.99 Average; 2.00 – 3.99 Fair; 0 – 1.99 Poor

Table 2 shows the results of the posttest score of the respondents after using the subject-integrated instructional material. Based on the results, there were changes in the mean of the score of the respondents. Identifying the Main idea got Table 2 shows the results of the posttest score of the respondents after using the subject-integrated instructional material. Based on the results, there were changes in the mean of the score of the respondents. Identifying the Main idea got the highest Mean of 4.80 followed by answering direct recall questions having Mean of 4.49. Both were found to Average level in the Least Mastered Reading Comprehension Skills.

Similarly, the surveyed respondents considering the third highest mean of 3.74 in terms of predicting outcomes are in the fair level after using the subject-integrated instructional material given. Based from Bailey (2015) predicting outcome is an important strategy in reading process. Thus, the students must practice this skill in daily basis [9].

Furthermore, identifying unfamiliar vocabulary despite of increase mean scores got the total Mean of 2.31 and revealed average level before and after using the subject-integrated instructional material. It indicates that with the use of integrated instructional materials it improves the reading comprehension skills of the pupils as Glende (2013) vocabularies strategies have positive impact in the ability of the pupils to comprehend contents [9]. Using contextual clues helps in the retention of the word vocabulary which is needed in the reading comprehension skills.

Lastly, the lowest Mean of 1.77 in terms of sequencing of events still in poor level despite of increase in the mean scores. It simply means that after employing the integrated instructional materials it helps in the enhancement of the least mastered reading comprehension skills in sequencing of events. With this, Gouldthorp et al. (2018) cited sequencing is an essential skill for the comprehension of the pupils which is improved through application of intervention programs and different instructional materials [10].

All of the results have a little improvement; however, it is not high as expected. The experiment shows that despite of using subject-integrated instructional material still they got a low score. It implies that the students have lack of interest in reading and they are not well-motivated. Therefore, the use of subject-integrated instructional material must be strengthened to bring back the interest and motivation of the students.

Thus, the subject-integrated instructional material should use by the students in daily basis to practice and enhance the reading comprehension skills. In addition, to bring back the interest and motivation of the students, the researcher must provide another interactive activity in the subject-integrated instructional material focusing in identifying the main idea and predicting outcomes that were not improve in the study.

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Table 3. Subject-Integrated Instructional Material in terms of Need-Based

Need-Based	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. The topics in the subject-integrated instructional material is enhancing my reading comprehension skills.	4.00	0.00	Highly Manifested
2. The activities help me to improve my skills in getting the main idea, predicting outcomes, sequencing events, answering direct recall questions, and finding the meaning of an unfamiliar words.	3.89	0.40	Highly Manifested
3. The subject-integrated instructional material helps me appreciate the love for reading because it contains different sentences, paragraphs, and stories.	3.97	0.17	Highly Manifested
Overall	3.95	0.14	Highly Manifested

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Highly Manifested; 2.50- 3.49 Manifested; 1.50-2.49 Less Manifested; 1.00-1.49 Not Manifested With an overall mean of 3.95, the respondents highly manifested the statements in need based as it is shown in table number 3.

In the statement 1 having Mean of 4.00 which made the surveyed respondents to Highly Manifested that need-based the topics in the subject-integrated instructional materials is enhancing the reading comprehensions of the learners.

Based on the results, the third statement shows the need based in the subject-integrated instructional material that helps the learners to appreciate the love for reading because it contains different sentences, paragraphs, and stories, which made the respondents to Highly Manifested with a Mean of 3.97. As stated by Shukla (2018) instructional materials can be used to involve students in reading activities [11].

Moreover, second statement which got the lowest Mean of 3.89 that made the respondents to Highly Manifested in the indicators that stated the need-based in the activities which help the learners to improve skills in getting the main idea, predicting outcomes, sequencing events, answering direct recall questions, and finding the meaning of an unfamiliar words. It means that instructional materials serve as tool to enhance the reading comprehension skills of the students (Nicoll, 2003) as cited by Bagui, et. al. (2008) [12].

Table 4. Subject-Integrated Instructional Material in terms of Content

Content	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. There are varied activities for the development of my reading skills.	4.00	0.00	Highly Manifested
2. The lessons and activities are appropriate for me as a grade five pupil because it is easy to understand.	3.89	0.32	Highly Manifested
3. The lessons and activities are applicable to me because they were simple and they improve my reading comprehension skills.	3.94	0.24	Highly Manifested
Overall	3.94	0.17	Highly Manifested

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Highly Manifested; 2.50- 3.49 Manifested; 1.50-2.49 Less Manifested; 1.00-1.49 Not Manifested Using subject-integrated instructional material in terms of content are being presented in Table 4. Respondents highly manifested with all the mentioned statements with an overall mean of 3.94.

The highest mean of 4.00 shows that most of the respondents Highly Manifested that there are varied activities for the development of my reading skills with the use of subject-integrated instructional materials in terms of Content.

Similarly, with a Mean of 3.94, the surveyed respondents Highly Manifested that the lessons and activities are applicable to the pupils because the materials were simple and helped in the improvement of reading comprehension skills. As stated by Funcion (2019), the instructional materials must be enjoyable to the learners and it should be consisted of different activities so that the students would learn better [13].

Lastly, respondents Highly Manifested with the indicators that stated that lessons and activities were appropriate to the grade level of the pupils thus making the respondents easily understand the content using integrated instructional materials got the lowest Mean of 3.89. Thus, Nombrefia (2004) concluded that the prepared materials should be in line with the subject mastery of the learners [14].

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Table 5. Subject-Integrated Instructional Material in terms of Standard Alignment (DepEd MELCs)

Standard Alignment (DepEd MELCs)	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. The objectives/ outcomes are aligned with the competencies that I needed in reading and writing.	4.00	0.00	Highly Manifested
2. The lessons and activities given are connected to the necessary skills that I needed to develop in the subject.	3.89	0.32	Highly Manifested
3. The lessons improve my reading skills.	3.89	0.32	Highly Manifested
Overall	3.92	0.22	Highly Manifested

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Highly Manifested; 2.50- 3.49 Manifested; 1.50-2.49 Less Manifested; 1.00-1.49 Not Manifested

As pictured in Table 5, respondents highly manifested with the statements based on the overall mean of 3.92. It indicates that using subject-integrated instructional material helps the respondents in developing reading comprehension skills in terms of standard alignment (DepEd MELCs). The concept and skills in the MELCs help the students to relate and apply it in their own environment (Llego, n.d.) [15].

As revealed by the highest Mean Value of 4.00, respondents Highly Manifested that objectives or outcomes are aligned with the competencies that pupils needed in reading and writing using subject-integrated instructional materials.

In addition, indicators 2 and 3 got the same Mean of 3.89 which made the surveyed respondents to Highly Manifested in the statements stating, the lessons and activities given are connected to the necessary skills that pupils needed to develop in the subject and the lessons improve the reading skills of the pupils. Based from Funcion (2019) instructional material is focused on the students' needs that are in line with the course objectives.

Table 6. Subject-Integrated Instructional Material in terms of Integration

Integration	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. The subject-integrated instructional material is important to me as a grade five pupil because it helps me to gain information from two or more subjects from the basic lesson.	3.97	0.17	Highly Manifested
2. The activities in the subject-integrated instructional material catch my interest because it also gives the importance of understanding the topic not only in one but two or more learning areas.	3.94	0.24	Highly Manifested
3. The topics in the subject-integrated instructional material bring information from two or more subjects that are aligned with the objectives.	4.00	0.00	Highly Manifested
Overall	3.97	0.09	Highly Manifested

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Highly Manifested; 2.50- 3.49 Manifested; 1.50-2.49 Less Manifested; 1.00-1.49 Not Manifested As can be gleaned from table 6, respondents highly manifested with an Overall Mean of 3.97.

The last statement got the highest Mean of 4.00 which cited the topics in the subject-integrated instructional material bring information from two or more subjects that are aligned with the objectives. With this, the surveyed respondents were Highly Manifested with the given indicator. According to Badley (2009), the integration process can encourage the students to recognize the connection between different contents [16].

Moreover, as revealed in the study, the subject-integrated instructional material is important to the respondents as grade five pupils since it helps to gain information from two or more subjects from the basic lesson and got the highest Mean of 3.97 which made respondents Highly Manifested with the stated indicator.

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Likewise in the study of Akintunde and Danlami (2018) noted that instructional materials stimulate the interest of the pupils that makes teaching more productive, meaningful sources of information and learning more valuable [17]. This is somehow connected in number 2 statement that obtained the lowest Mean of 3.94 which mention about the activities in the subject-integrated instructional material which catch the interest of the respondents because it gives the importance of understanding the topic not only in one but two or more learning areas.

Table 7. Subject-Integrated Instructional Material in terms of Graphics

Graphics	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. The images captured my interest because it makes me understand of the content easier.	3.97	0.17	Highly Manifested
2. The images give me additional idea on the topic because it gives clue in the lesson.	3.97	0.17	Highly Manifested
3. It has a colorful presentation that catches my interest to read more.	4.00	0.00	Highly Manifested
Overall	3.98	0.08	Highly Manifested

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Highly Manifested; 2.50- 3.49 Manifested; 1.50-2.49 Less Manifested; 1.00-1.49 Not Manifested

Table 7 presents the summary of the perceptions of the respondents in using subject-integrated instructional material in terms of graphics. Respondents highly manifested all the statements set as it has an overall mean of 3.98.

Moreover, with the highest Mean of 4.00 for the statement instructional materials has a colorful presentation that catches the interest of the respondents to read more. With this, the respondents Highly Manifested that colorful graphic presentation gives motivation to be involve in reading and increase comprehending what the passage all about. Based on Bukoye (2019) as cited by Castillo (2021), instructional materials allow the students to interact with words, symbols, and ideas that help them to develop their abilities especially reading [18].

Having same Mean of 3.97, the respondents Highly Manifested that images capture interest that makes the content easier to understand and give additional idea on the topic using clue in the lesson. According to Hibek (2015) as cited by Castillo (2021), modules associated with images and text can increase students understanding and improve their skills and ability by their own [19].

Table 8. Difference between the pretest and post-test scores of the respondents before and after using subject-integrated instructional material

Least Mastered Reading Comprehension Skills	Pretest		Posttest		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				Lower	Upper
Identifying Main Idea	4.43	1.44	4.80	1.97	-1.49	34	.146	-.879	.136
Sequencing of Events	0.94	1.28	1.77	1.80	-2.31	34	.027	-1.557	-.100
Answering Direct Recall Questions	3.40	2.53	4.49	2.33	-2.64	34	.012	-1.920	-.251
Predicting Outcomes	4.23	2.41	3.74	2.31	1.38	34	.176	-.228	1.199
Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary	3.20	1.94	2.31	1.62	2.97	34	.005	.280	1.491

Legend: If p-value (Sig.) < 0.05, then it is statistically significant.

If p-value (Sig.) > 0.05, then it is NOT statistically significant.

Table 3 presents the significant difference between the pretest and post-test after the treatment. Results show that the mean posttest score in terms of identifying the main idea (4.80) is higher than the mean score in the pretest (4.43), representing that there was not significant improvement in reading in terms of this skill. These data were subjected to statistical analysis which revealed that there is no significant difference ($t=1.49$; $p=.146$) between the pretest and posttest of the respondents after using subject-integrated instructional material. Thus, the researcher should provide an interactive activity that would help the students to improve this skill. In terms of sequencing of events, the mean posttest score (1.77) is also higher than the mean pretest of the respondents representing a significant improvement in reading comprehension skills. However, when tested at a .05 level of significant difference, the p-

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value of -2.31 shows no significant difference at all. With the use of subject-integrated instructional material, only a minimal increase in the mean was shown. Thus, the hypothesis is supported in this study.

Based from the study of Nodirovna (2020) and Misbahuddin (2017) sequencing of events considered as key in comprehension and can help to improve the reading comprehension skills of the students [20], [21].

In terms of answering direct recall questions, the mean posttest score (4.49) is also higher than the mean pretest score (3.40) representing an improvement after using the subject-integrated instructional material. Results revealed that using subject-integrated instructional material found no significant difference ($t=2.64$; $p=.012$) in terms of answering direct recall questions.

In terms of predicting outcomes, the mean posttest score (3.74) is lower than the mean pretest score (4.23). Results revealed that the respondents found difficulties in studying the topic which is predicting outcomes. However, the t -value of 1.38 and p -value of .176 reveal that there is no significant difference at .05 levels. With this regard, the researcher must focus in teaching this skill so that it would also improve just like the other skills of reading comprehension.

However, in the study of Sumirat, et al. (2019) stated that large number of students had a difficulty in understanding English text which is the same with the result of the present study which made lower than the mean pre-test. With this, the current study proved that prediction strategy has significant impact on the reading comprehension of the students which is different from the present result.

In identifying unfamiliar vocabulary, the mean post-test score (2.31) is higher than the mean pretest score (3.20). It shows that the respondents decrease their reading comprehension skills in terms of identifying unfamiliar vocabulary after using subject-integrated instructional material. However, the t -value of 2.97 and p -value of .005 reveal that there is a significant difference at .05 levels.

It indicates that more use of instructional materials is needed to further increase the results when it comes to identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. It is supported by Iltter (2019) which gave evidence that lack of vocabulary word is the main reason why pupils failed in comprehending text that affect their reading activities [22].

Overall results show that the respondents have no significant difference before and after using the subject-integrated instructional material. These results may be affected by the fact that the respondents have limited information regarding the topics. One reason is that the respondents came from two years of modular distance learning modality (MDL), wherein pupils are being guided by their parents, guardians, or tutors at home, and some of them are just learning by themselves during the pandemic. However, subject-integrated instructional material may serve as a supplementary material in enhancing reading comprehension skills.

To sum up all, it simply means that use of subject-integrated instructional material can be a great help in improving the reading comprehension skills of the pupils. With the help of the said materials can provide more capability to enhance comprehending passage through different activities such identifying the main idea, sequencing of events, answering direct recall questions, predicting outcomes, and lastly identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. Likewise, Adamu & Fati (2020) proved that using instructional materials can help to have an effective teaching and learning process that enhance the reading skills of the students [23].

CONCLUSION

1. The reading performance of the respondents in the mean pre-test scores before using the subject-integrated instructional materials were both Average in terms of identifying the main Idea and predicting outcomes followed with the same Fair Level in terms of answering direct recall questions and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. Lastly, sequencing of events found in the poor level.
2. In the post-test scores of the respondents after using the subject-integrated instructional materials revealed both Average in terms of identifying the main Idea and answering direct recall questions. Fair Level in terms of predicting outcomes and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. Lastly, in terms of sequencing of events still in poor level despite of increase in the mean scores.
3. However, despite of no differences in pre-test and post-test, there was still a minimal improvement in a certain aspect. Integrating this material is somehow affected by the timeframe given to the respondents.
4. Majority of the respondents highly manifested in perceptions of the use of subject-integrated instructional materials in terms of need-based, content, standard alignment (DepEd MELCs), integration and graphics were helpful in improving reading comprehension skills of the pupils.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the drawn conclusions, the following recommendations were formulated:

1. The subject-integrated instructional material can use by the teachers to enhance different reading comprehension skills such as the sequencing of events, answering direct recall questions, and identifying the unfamiliar vocabulary of the students.
2. This material should consist of more interactive activities that encourage the students to enhance their reading comprehension skills, particularly in identifying the main idea and predicting outcomes. Also, provide a longer time to expose the students to the lessons in the subject-integrated instructional material.
3. Future researchers may conduct a similar study using other reading comprehension skills to assess the effectiveness of the material in enhancing other reading comprehension skills of the students.

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